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The Reduction of Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disabilities in the Italian Regions

On average, the value of fatal accidents and permanent disabilities decreased in Italy by about 4.1 units in the transition between 2008 and 2018.

Inail calculates the value of the rate of moral injuries and permanent disability. This indicator is defined as the "Number of fatal accidents and accidents with permanent disability out of the total employed (net of perhaps armed) per 10,000". This indicator is present in the ISTAT-BES report. The data with reference to 2018 can be analyzed in the form of a ranking on a regional basis.

The ranking of the Italian regions by rate of fatal injuries and permanent disability in the Italian regions in 2018. Basilicata is in first place for the value of the rate of fatal injuries and permanent disability in 2018 with a value of 23.2, followed by Calabria with a value equal to 17.1 and from Abruzzo with a value equal to an amount of 17. In the middle of the table there are Molise with an amount equal to 13.6, Emilia-Romagna with an amount equal to 13.3 and Puglia with an amount equal to 12.6. Piedmont closes the ranking with an amount equal to 7.9, Lombardy with a value equal to 7.6 units on a par with Lazio.

The variation between the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability between 2008 and 2018 in the Italian regions. The data in the Istat-BES database allow us to analyze the variation between 2008 and 2018 in the trend in the rate of fatal injuries and permanent disability. Basilicata ranks first in terms of the variation in the rate of fatal injuries and permanent disability with a value of 0.4 units, followed by Liguria and Veneto with a tie with an amount equal to -2.1. In the middle of the table there are Sicily and Calabria with a value of -4.6 units, followed by Molise with a value of -4.8 units and Tuscany with a value of -5.00. Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Emilia-Romagna close the ranking with a value of -7.2 units followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of -8.5 units and Umbria equal to a value of -9, 5 units.

North. The number of accidents and disabilities decreased in the North in the period between 2014 and 2018. In 2014 the value of accidents and disability was equal to 11.20 units and decreased to a value of 10, 00 units in 2018 or equal to a change of -1.20 units equal to a value of -10.71%. Hereinafter, the expression "Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disabilities" will be placed in the acronym IMIP. In the transition between 2014 and 2015 the value of IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 11.20 units up to a value equal to 10.90 units or equal to a change of -0.30 units equal to a value of - 2.68%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 10.90 units up to a value equal to 10.80 units or equal to a change of -0.10 units equal to a value of - 0.92%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 10.80 units up to a value equal to 10.50 units or equal to a variation of -0.30 units equal to a value of -2 , 78%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of IMIP decreased from an amount of 10.50 units to a value of 10.00 units.

Center. The value of IMIP in the center decreased in the passage between 2014 and 2018 from an amount equal to 13.30 units up to a value equal to 11.80 units or equal to a change of -1.50 units

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equal to 11, 28%. In the passage between 2015 and 2016 the value of the IMIP in the center increased from an amount equal to 12.80 units up to a value equal to 12.90 units or equal to a change of 0.10 units equal to a value of 0.78%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 12.90 to a value of 12.50 units or equal to a variation of -0.40 units equal to a value of 3, 10%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the IMIP in the center decreased from an amount equal to 12.50 units up to a value equal to 11.80 units or equal to a change of -0.70 units equal to a value of -5.60%.

South of Italy. The value of the IMIP in the Mezzogiorno decreased from a value equal to 15.60 units up to a value equal to 13.60 units in the transition between 2014 and 2018 or a variation equal to an amount of -2.00 equivalent units at a value of -12.82%. In the passage between 2014 and 2015 the value of the IMIP in the South has decreased from an amount of 15.60 units up to a value equal to 15.20 units or equal to a value of -0.40 units equal to a value of -2.56%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 15.20 units up to a value equal to 14.60 units or equal to a variation of -0.60 units equal to an amount of -3.95%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 14.60 units up to a value equal to 14.20 units or equal to a variation of -0.40 units equal to a value of -2.74%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the IMIP decreased from an amount equal to 14.20 units up to a value of 13.60 units or equal to a value of -0.60 units equal to a value of -4.23%.

. A clustering with k-means algorithm and representation with t-SNE algorithms is also carried out which, considering the 2008-2018 time series, and focusing attention on 2018, identifies the following three clusters - or groupings - of regions:

- Cluster 1: Trentino Alto Adige, Tuscany, Sicily, Molise, Liguria, Emilia-Romagna;
- Cluster 2: Umbria, Sardinia, Marche, Calabria, Basilicata, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 3: Veneto, Valle d'Aosta, Puglia, Piedmont, Lombardy, Lazio, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Campania.

Clustering is carried out to verify if there is a repetition of the North-Center-South dynamics of the data. This dynamic is certainly to be excluded in the case of the observed variable. In fact, the regions present in the clusters show high degrees of geographic heterogeneity.

Conclusions. As is evident in the data that have been analyzed, the number of IMIPs has significantly decreased in the various Italian regions and macro-regions. On average, the value between 2008 and 2018 decreased in Italy by about 4.1 units. The reduction in the number of IMIPs may be due to two factors of a sociological-industrial and IT-technological nature:

- Reduction in the percentage of workers in the primary and secondary sector: in fact, it is necessary to consider that about 1 million workers have made the transition from the primary and secondary sector to the tertiary sector since the 2007 crisis and on the occasion of the turbo-capitalist effects of globalization. This reduction may have had a very significant impact in also reducing the value of the IMIPs.
- Increase of automation and applications of artificial intelligence in primary and secondary industries: it must also be considered that many activities in the primary and secondary sector have been significantly automated and subjected to the orientation of the Internet of Things type, in the creation of the smart factory, with application of industry 5.0. These technological innovations lead to further functional unemployment and in reducing the number of employees they also reduce the risks of IMIP.

It is likely that the value of IMIP will be further reduced in the future, effectively determining the marginality of INAIL as a social welfare institution in the workplace. In this regard, a comprehensive reform of the labor institutions would be necessary to prepare the workforce for the new economic challenges in the post-Covid 19 phase.

Declarations

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Appendix

Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente

Rank	Regione	2018
1	<i>Basilicata</i>	23,2
2	<i>Calabria</i>	17,1
3	<i>Abruzzo</i>	17
4	<i>Umbria</i>	16,7
5	<i>Marche</i>	15,9
6	<i>Sardegna</i>	15,6
7	<i>Toscana</i>	15,3
8	<i>Liguria</i>	14,5
9	<i>Sicilia</i>	13,8
10	<i>Molise</i>	13,6
11	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	13,3
12	<i>Puglia</i>	12,6
13	<i>Veneto</i>	12,2
14	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	11,8
15	<i>Campania</i>	10,3
16	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	10,1
17	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	8,9
18	<i>Piemonte</i>	7,9
19	<i>Lombardia</i>	7,6
19	<i>Lazio</i>	7,6

Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente nelle macroregioni italiane. Fonte: INAIL

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014-2018
Nord	★ 11,20	★ 10,90	★ 10,80	★ 10,50	★ 10,00	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		★ -0,30	★ -0,10	★ -0,30	★ -0,50	★ -1,20
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		★ -2,68	★ -0,92	★ -2,78	★ -4,76	★ -10,71
Centro	★ 13,30	★ 12,80	★ 12,90	★ 12,50	★ 11,80	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		★ -0,50	★ 0,10	★ -0,40	★ -0,70	★ -1,50
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		★ -3,76	★ 0,78	★ -3,10	★ -5,60	★ -11,28
Mezzogiorno	★ 15,60	★ 15,20	★ 14,60	★ 14,20	★ 13,60	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		★ -0,40	★ -0,60	★ -0,40	★ -0,60	★ -2,00
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		★ -2,56	★ -3,95	★ -2,74	★ -4,23	★ -12,82
Italia	★ 12,80	★ 12,40	★ 12,20	★ 11,90	★ 11,30	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		★ -0,40	★ -0,20	★ -0,30	★ -0,60	★ -1,50
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		★ -3,13	★ -1,61	★ -2,46	★ -5,04	★ -11,72

Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente 2008-2018. Fonte: INAIL

Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente 2008-2018. Fonte: INAIL

Rank	Regione	2008-2018
1	<i>Basilicata</i>	0,4
2	<i>Liguria</i>	-2,1
2	<i>Veneto</i>	-2,1
3	<i>Campania</i>	-2,5
4	<i>Abruzzo</i>	-2,9
4	<i>Puglia</i>	-2,9
5	<i>Lazio</i>	-3
6	<i>Lombardia</i>	-3,1
7	<i>Piemonte</i>	-3,2
8	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	-4,1
9	<i>Calabria</i>	-4,6
9	<i>Sicilia</i>	-4,6
10	<i>Molise</i>	-4,8
11	<i>Toscana</i>	-5
12	<i>Sardegna</i>	-5,1
13	<i>Marche</i>	-5,8
14	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	-7,2
14	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	-7,2
15	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	-8,5
16	<i>Umbria</i>	-9,5

Feature 1	Cluster	Silhouette
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	C1	0.669998
Toscana	C1	0.569754
Sicilia	C1	0.688963
Molise	C1	0.668531
Liguria	C1	0.661657
Emilia-Romagna	C1	0.676297
Umbria	C2	0.611622
Sardegna	C2	0.529058
Marche	C2	0.573232
Calabria	C2	0.609881
Basilicata	C2	0.622432
Abruzzo	C2	0.551936
Veneto	C3	0.626519
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	C3	0.638936
Puglia	C3	0.513806
Piemonte	C3	0.683533
Lombardia	C3	0.674019
Lazio	C3	0.678635
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	C3	0.640703
Campania	C3	0.666098

Infortuni Mortali ed Inabilità Permanenti nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane. Fonte: Inail.

Tassi di Infortuni Mortali ed Inabilità Permanenti nel 2018. Fonte: INAIL.

